

THE EFFECT OF COLLOIDS ON THE ELECTRO-DEPOSITION OF NICKEL ON COPPER.

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The effect of chromium, molybdenum, tellurium and tungsten sols on the electro-deposition of nickel has been investigated and the nature of the deposits studied.

The action of inorganic colloids on the electrodeposition of nickel on copper has been investigated in this laboratory by Puri and co-workers (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 16, 71, 581; 1940, 17, 699; Sir S. S. Bhatnagar Commemoration Vol., 1941, p. 33, 59) and the results have been very satisfactory. The basic idea of this study is to find a colloid, the addition of which to the nickel plating bath, should make the deposit hard, smooth and shining and also make the electroplating of nickel easier and cheaper.

The effect of sulphur, selenium and iodine sols has been studied previously. In the present investigation the effect of chromium, molybdenum, tellurium and tungsten sols has been studied.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The bath employed and other experimental details were the same as used by us previously (Puri and Seth, *loc. cit.*). A current of 0.2 ampere was used throughout the experiment.

Preparation and Concentration of the Colloids.

Chromium Hydroxide Sol.—Ammonia was added to a boiling solution of chromium chloride to precipitate $\text{Cr}(\text{OH})_3$. Excess of ammonia was expelled. The precipitate was filtered and thoroughly washed. Half of the precipitate was dissolved in hydrochloric acid and the rest added to it. CrCl_3 peptised the precipitate. On dilution a beautiful green sol was obtained. This was positively charged. (Neidle and Barab, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1916, 38, 1962; 1917, 39, 71). The sol was estimated as Cr_2O_3 .

Molybdenum Sol.—It was obtained by the peptising action of dilute hydrochloric acid on the metal formed by the reduction of the oxide with zinc dust. The dialysed sol was light brown in transmitted light and grey in reflected light. The sol was found to be positively charged (Wedekind and Jochem, *Z. angew. Chem.*, 1927, 40, 434).

Tellurium Sol.—Telluric acid (0.5 g.) was suspended in 50 c.c. of boiling water to which was added hydrazine hydrate drop by drop until turbidity

occured. It was diluted to 250 c.c. when a rich brown sol was obtained. This was negatively charged (Doloan, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1925, **29**, 178).

Tungsten Trioxide Sol.—Sodium tungstate was acidified in cold with dilute hydrochloric acid when a yellow gel was thrown down. Repeated washings peptised the gel. It was negatively charged (Van Beimmelen's Gedenkbuch, 1910, p. 152; *Kolloid Z.*, 1914, **18**, 145).

Manganese Dioxide Sol.—It was obtained by adding slowly 100 c.c. of 6% potassium permanganate to a cold solution containing 5 g. of glucose in 20 c.c. of water together with a few c.c. of 10% sodium hydroxide. The mixture became rapidly viscous and after some time changed to a stable limpid sol (Witzemann, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, **37**, 1079; 1917, **39**, 27).

Effect of Colloids.

Chromium Hydroxide Sol.—With 3 c.c. the deposit is hard and shining but there are a few black specks here and there. With 5 c.c. there is a definite reduction in grain-size. The deposit is close-grained and microcrystalline. Even the side, opposite to the cathode, shows good deposit. Addition of 7 c.c. of the colloid diminished the brightness indicating that the maximum quantity of the colloid has been added.

Molybdenum Sol.—With 5 c.c. the deposit is very bright and hard. The surface is smooth and lustrous. Addition of 7 c.c. of the colloid decreases the lustre, while with 10 c.c. the brightness vanishes and the deposit looks pretty dull.

Tellurium Sol.—Its results are comparable to selenium sol. With 5 c.c. the deposit is very shining, coherent and microcrystalline. All the defects in the original plate disappeared. The surface could take a high polish. Addition of 10 c.c. of the colloid gives a coherent and shining deposit, but its brightness slightly decreases. On the addition of 15 c.c. the crystal size increases and the deposit becomes coarse and less hard, indicating that optimum concentration of the colloid has reached.

Tungsten Trioxide Sol.—The addition of 1 c.c. of this sol makes the nickel deposit shining and hard. With 3 c.c. of the colloid the deposit is quite good but not very thick as at places the surface of copper is visible. With 5 c.c. of the colloid effect is more potent, the deposit is very bright and adherent and microphotographs show a considerable reduction in grain-size. The addition, however, of 7 c.c. of the colloid makes the deposit non-coherent and crystalline (*vide* table below).

Manganese Dioxide Sol.—Addition of 5 c.c. of the colloid improves the hardness of the deposit but does not effect the brightness at all; addition of

7 c.c. improves the lusture and gives an ideal deposit with this colloid. Addition of 10 c.c. again diminishes the lusture.

The table below indicates briefly the quantity of colloid used in each case and the effect on the nature of the deposit.

Colloid.	Colloid added.		Ni deposited.		Nature of the deposit
	(c.c.)	(g./400 c.c.)	Actual.	Calc.	
Nil	0	0'00	0'1132 g.	0'1141 g.	Deposit is shining. Abrasion marks visible.
Chromium hydroxide sol	3	0'000048	0'1131	0'1161	Deposit very hard and shining.
	5	0'000080	0'1061	0'1084	Ideal deposit. Very shining and hard, micro crystalline. Defects of original plate absent.
	7	0'000112	0'1124	0'1163	Deposit less shining and crystalline.
Molybdenum sol	5	0'0025	0'0974	0'0994	Smooth, hard and mirror-like shining deposit. Microcrystalline in structure.
	7	0'0035	0'0963	0'0996	Less shining. Uniform and hard deposit.
	10	0'0050	0'1010	0'1090	Hard but dull looking, crystalline in appearance.
Tellurium sol	5	0'00066	0'1096	0'1126	Deposit very shining and microcrystalline. Could take a high polish.
	10	0'00132	0'1096	0'1135	Deposit hard but less shining.
	15	0'00198	0'1207	0'1257	Deposit rough and crystalline. Optimum concentration reached.
Tungsten trioxide sol	3	0'00020	0'1118	0'1158	Addition of colloid slightly improves the deposit, but copper surface is visible at places.
	5	0'00033	0'1155	0'1181	Deposit lustrous, hard and fine-grained.
	7	0'00047	0'1112	0'1144	Deposit less shining and crystalline. Optimum concentration reached.
Manganese dioxide sol	5	0'0375	0'1042	0'1051	Uniform, hard and microcrystalline deposit. Practically ideal deposit, close-grained, lustrous and hard,
	7	0'0525	0'0956	0'0958	
	10	0'0750	0'1152	0'1169	Less shining and hard than with 7 c.c.

DISCUSSION.

From the above account it is proved beyond doubt that the addition of the colloids of the elements of groups VI and VII improves the deposit in brightness as well as in hardness; the only exception is sulphur, which being a non-metal, shows a different result. Iodine similarly in the next group, though gives quite a coherent deposit, lacks lusture completely. Another fact which this study reveals is that metallic colloids impart lustre to the nickel deposit, while oxide sols render the deposit very hard and uniform. Selenium, tellurium and molybdenum sols, in our opinion, will help the uniform and coherent deposition of nickel considerably. With molybdenum sol, the brightness is of such an order that a perfectly reflecting surface was obtained. Tungsten trioxide sol was the only one that gave a bright as well as a very hard deposit.

Further work on this problem is still proceeding in this laboratory.

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